

THE DEVELOPMENT OF LEGAL EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN IS THE KEY TO PROGRESS

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Abstract. *This article presents the concepts of legal education, the prospects for the formation of the rule of law and civil society, as well as the role and importance of legal education in raising the legal awareness and legal culture of young people, issues of further improvement of cooperation between state, non-governmental and non-profit organizations in the implementation of legal education.*

Keywords: *legal education, legal education, effectiveness of legal education and legal education, legal awareness, legal culture, elevation of legal culture.*

The age-old dream of every state, whose main goal is to build a highly developed rule of law and a just civil society, is to raise the level of legal awareness and legal culture of its people. The social development of any State depends on the legal culture of the citizens of that State. Indeed, a highly developed legal awareness and legal culture are an integral feature of the rule of law and civil society. A high level of legal awareness and legal culture is a product of legal education. Legal education plays a key role in the formation of legal awareness and legal culture of the population.

In this regard, the Republic of Uzbekistan pays special attention to lawmaking, enforcement of adopted laws, legal education and upbringing at the level of state policy. As President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted in his speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan: "... while ensuring the rule of law, it is important to enhance legal culture, educate citizens in the spirit of respect for the law."

Legal education and legal education are concepts that are closely interrelated and represent various aspects of social life, one of which presupposes the presence of the other. This is a complex and multifaceted social phenomenon, the process of pedagogical influence, which is reflected in the legal consciousness of individuals and social groups, is purposeful, planned and carried out using special methods of

In the system of social education, as well as other types of education, legal education is of particular importance. Legal education is formed and developed on the basis of moral, cultural, spiritual, political, legal and other types of social education. In short, legal education is closely related to all types of social education.

To make the right choice of educational tools, it is important to identify the factors that shape a person's personality, such as: social status, education system, family, society, and so on. To educate a person means to take into account all these factors.

The educational effect of education is that it creates conditions for people to adhere to advanced political, legal, moral and other views, provides an opportunity to master important principles and basic rules of public life. Cultural and legal education of a person characterizes the level of his personal consciousness, expresses his psyche, worldview and values, and also determines a person's actions in the field of law and order.

The development of our society in the 21st century requires that legal education and upbringing be carried out in a systematic, scientifically based manner, covering all segments of society, age groups. To do this, it is important to coordinate the activities of educational institutions, literature, art, mass media, and special legal institutions in the field of legal education and upbringing.

At the same time, there are requirements and conditions that must be met in the process of legal education and upbringing, namely: firstly, legal education forms an independent legal consciousness, which requires the search and application of specific forms and methods of education. Persons engaged in the implementation of legal education, educators themselves should be equipped with the necessary amount of legal knowledge, they should have legal knowledge, high legal culture; Secondly, the active participation of students is important for improving the effectiveness of the legal education process.

The ultimate goal of legal education and upbringing is the formation of a person who has a high level of respect for law and order and has legal activity and a sense of intolerance to wrongdoing. Legal activity is voluntary, conscious, proactive, socially and morally responsible behavior of this person. In this sense, the interaction of legal and moral culture is important. It is as an integral part of moral culture that moral consciousness encourages a person to act in accordance with the requirements of the law.

Thus, legal education and upbringing is an important and integral part of social education, the effective implementation of which serves as the basis for the formation of a high sense of justice and legal culture in society, the establishment of a strong social and legal order, the creation of a rule of law and civil society.

Legal education in a broad sense is the sum of legal knowledge acquired by a person through legal education in the family and kindergarten, self-enrichment of his legal knowledge, independent work on himself as a whole.

In general, legal education is a special activity of state bodies, non-governmental organizations, officials and groups of persons aimed at improving the legal awareness and legal culture of the population.

The essence of legal education consists in the formation of legal guidance, attitudes, motives for actions in the field regulated by law. With the help of legal education, a person develops an attitude towards the law as a value, obeys the law, develops respect for the state as a phenomenon that ensures the stability of society, develops its cooperation with state bodies and public organizations in strengthening law and order.

It should be noted that the education of legal awareness is not only the expansion of knowledge about the law, the formation of a positive attitude towards it as a social value. At the same time, the education of legal skills and habits is very important.

The conducted research shows that in most cases, offenders and law-abiding citizens have almost the same level of knowledge of the law. However, the attitude towards law and the acquisition of legal behavior skills differ significantly.

Legal education and upbringing is a complex phenomenon in its structure. Researchers identify three interrelated aspects of legal education and upbringing: the first is the formation of a system of legal knowledge (the immediate goal); the second is the formation of a firm belief (an intermediate goal); the third is the formation of legal, socially active behavior, habits and skills.

As a result of legal education and upbringing, the following difficult tasks are solved: first, students learn to evaluate their own behavior and the behavior of others, develop skills for the independent application of legal knowledge acquired in practice; secondly, the formation of guidelines for the implementation of only legitimate actions in accordance with the law and other normative legal acts; and Thirdly, to develop the quality of intolerance towards any crime. The legal knowledge gained in this way serves to create a system of strict observance of the law in any situation, and to carry out a rapid fight against an offense.

Mastering legal education and upbringing is a process that can be carried out at a certain stage of a person's life. The lack of training for a certain period of time makes it difficult to master it at later stages. This is primarily due to the age characteristics of a person, which is associated with a decrease in his ability to learn, external influences in the form of education.

Legal education is an important social tool that allows citizens to acquire legal knowledge, influence a person in an organized, systematic and clear manner, form their legal awareness, legal instructions, law-abiding behavior skills and habits.

There is a narrow and broad interpretation of legal education in the legal literature. In a narrow sense, legal education is understood as the sum of the legal knowledge that people receive in law schools. Legal education is a positive human activity in a system that leads to a common goal, consciously based on the development and policy of society. Legal self-education of a person is the conscious formation of a positive legal direction in his character on the way to a specific goal.

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